

DEFORESTATION RATE ANALYSIS IN BAYELSA STATE FROM REMOTELY SENSED DATA

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Abstract: *Deforestation has been noticed of recent as one of the most intense ecological challenges in the Niger Delta Nigeria where Bayelsa has been at the centre stage. This study area with a human population of 1,704,515 according to National Population census 2006 considered the extent and degree of deforestation between 2008 and 2018 using remote sensing technique. The objectives of the study include: To demonstrate how remotely sensed data can be used to perform spatial, change detection and analysis, to come up with proper policies that can reduce deforestation rate in the study area. This article provides a spatial analytical framework of the rate of deforestation within 10 years in the area using satellite imageries that were geo-referenced and geo-processed in ArcGIS 10.6 to world coordinate system. Land use/land cover change analysis was carried out to know how the land, vegetation, water and other land covers have changed within the period of study. Data sources were obtained from the United States Geological Surveys (USGS) database. Change detection was used to analyze the rate of deforestation in the area by integrating the analytical tools of geographic information systems (GIS) with remote sensing. A very high classification accuracy of 96.48% in 2008 imagery and 94.53% in 2018 was recorded. Training samples were used and Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) in order to estimate the percentage area of these features. The total area of vegetation in 2008(imagery band 7,4,3) was 5610.1km² while in 2018(imagery band 7,5,3) decreases to 5414.0km² with 191.1km² (which is about 3.49%) vegetation lost within the ten (10) years in the study area indicating deforestation. The impact of this on the ecosystem has been increased flooding, soil erosion as well as habitat loss. Accurate land use planning seems to be an efficient measure to preserve the mangrove swamp and coastal environment. The study therefore amongst others recommended ecosystem management strategies by policy makers to ameliorate the situation.*

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1.0 Introduction

Over the years, the Niger Delta region has suffered extensive environmental degradation caused by oil exploration activities leading to a considerable damage to its natural resource and ecosystem (Chijioke *et al*, 2025). Illegal logging is on the increase and the driving force for notable destruction in Nigeria Niger Delta region (Akpomorere *et al*, 2024). Human activities mainly oil drilling and extraction greatly threaten the biodiversity in the Niger Delta (Aransiola *et al*, 2024). Research indicates that local communities particularly those in oil producing areas suffer disproportionately from oil spills, gas flaring and deforestation (Ewim *et al*, 2023).

Deforestation is defined by the intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC) as the permanent removal of forest cover and the withdrawal of land from forest use, whether deliberately or circumstantially (Ekwugha *et. al.*, 2020).

Deforestation is often driven by government or private sector supported policies for agriculture and timber or wood industry. Deforestation can result from selective logging, grazing within forests, cutting etc.

Deforestation can as well be described as an ecological risk that has bringing about ecosystem imbalance in nature. Factors such as excessive farming, logging, Bush burning, petroleum exploration coupled with associated oil spills pollution, road construction, industrialization are cause of forest cover degradation (Ekpenyong, 2015).

World Bank (2016) reports that health forest support the livelihood of 1.6 billion people

globally who are amongst the developing cities of the world? Forest degradation occurs when forest ecosystem loses their capacity to provide important goods and services to the people and nature (IUCN, 2019).

Underlying drivers of deforestation are the broader, economic, political, technological, cultural and demographic factors and the fundamental social processes that strengthen the proximate factors of deforestation. Excessive logging activities in the Niger Delta region have led to the emergence of active soil erosion sites, compounded by heavy rainfall in the region (Piacentini *et.al*,2018). Policy and institutional factors play a significant role in deforestation rates.

There has been a serious deforestation in Bayelsa state due to oil and gas explorations, woods for timber business as well as fetching firewood by rural dwellers. There is therefore the need to come up with scientific analysis on the rate of deforestation in the study area and come up with sustainable management strategies.

Deforestation of an area can also be determined from geo-spatial techniques producing maps and images from remotely sensed data which was deployed in this study. The use of maps derived from satellite images are known for mapping impacts of floods, erosions, oilspills, landslides, cyclones, deforestations, droughts etc (Ndukwe, 1997). Birsen and Engin, 2009 also uses post-classification change detection analyses in their study of land use and land cover mapping.

The rate of loss of vegetative covering or deforestation of an area can as well be identified

from remotely sensed imageries or other spatial dataset or techniques using technique such as drones mapping whose changes in images such as forest loss can be identified image spatial analysis.

Change detection by comparing images from different periods, makes analysts to identify areas where forest cover has been lost or degraded. Vegetation indices-algorithms in image analysis like normalized difference vegetation index uses the difference between near infrared and red light to assess forest health and detection changes. GIS and remote sensing technology have on several cases provides instruments for monitoring deforestation, evaluating environment risks.

One significant advantage of using remote sensing is that it is time enabling with a large coverage capability using satellite imageries, multi-spectrally and spatio-temporarily.

Udoka *et.al*, 2015 in their own studies also presented an analysis of land cover changes due to forest loss in coastal states of the Niger Delta where Bayelsa occupies a central place.

Land cover change detection is necessary to update land cover maps and the management of natural resources (Defries *et.al*; 1995).

The availability of satellite data has made enormous impacts in the field of remote sensing such as Land use/Land cover mapping (Lo, 1986). The use of remote sensing in environmental studies have been applied in successful ecological zones mapping and risk analysis (Forman & Gordon, 1986).

The present condition in the Niger Delta marred by severe environmental degradation, primarily sterling from oil exploration activities and deforestation (Akpomurere and Uguru, 2020). Sparse tree diversity is an indication of disrupted habitat degradation and retarded

regeneration process (Bodo *et.al*, 2021). The science of remote sensing offers a practical means of frequent and monitoring of the environment by providing area-wide data needed for environmental and natural resource management (Bengt, 1992).

This study analyzes deforestation trend in Bayelsa State between 2008 and 2018 using remotely sensed imageries. The deforestation trend assessment in this study was done for land cover change detection using ERDAS imagine 14.0 and analyzed in ArcGIS 10.6 environment to detect changes on the land cover classes.

1.1 Study Area Description

Bayelsa state was created on October 1st 1996 and is geographically located within latitude 4° 45¹N and 5° 23¹N and Longitude 5° 15¹E and 6° 15¹E, with the West and Mid belt of the Nigerian Transverse Mercator (NTM) projection and with an estimated population of 1,704,515 people National Population Commission (NPC) 2006. The state is bounded to the North by Delta State, to the East by Rivers State, and to the West and South by the Atlantic Ocean. The Gulf of Guinea lies to the South. It has eight (8) Local Government Areas namely: Brass, Nembe, Ogbia, Yenagoa, Southern Ijaw, Kolokuma/Opukuma, Sagbama and Ekeremor as shown on the study area map (See Figures 1.1 and 1.2), with Yenagoa as its headquarters. Bayelsa state covers an area of 9415.8km². The state is in the tropical rainforest and mangrove swamp and lies almost entirely below sea level. The major socio-economic activities in the area include: fishing, farming. Palm wine tapping, timber and lumbering, local gin business, palm oil as well as oil and gas exploration by multinationals operating in the area (Turner, 2015).

Figure1.1: Map of Nigeria showing Bayelsa state.

Source: (Authour's Work, 2025)

Figure.1.2: Map of Bayelsa State (Study Area Map)

Source: (Authour’s Work, 2025)

1.2 Study Area Demographic Studies

Table 1.1: Total Population of Bayelsa State by LGA’s

S/No.	L.G.A	Population
1.	Brass	184,127
2.	Nembe	130,966
3.	Ogbia	179,606
4.	Southen Ijaw	321,808
5.	Yenagoa	352,285
6.	Kolokuma/Opukuma	79,266
7.	Ekeremor	269,588
8.	Sagbama	186,869
	Total Population	1,704,515

Source: National Population Census (NPC), 2006

Table 1.1 shows the population distribution of local Government areas in Bayelsa State (study area) with a population of 1,704,514 covering a land mass of about 9474km².

2.0 Materials and Methods

Materials deployed in the studies includes the administrative map of Bayelsa state which was acquired from the office of the Surveyor-General of Bayelsa state and satellite images derived from United State Geological Surveys (USGS) data

Enhancement

The use of multi-temporal satellite data for large area mapping was having a number of challenges including geometric correction errors, noise arising from atmospheric effects and changing illumination errors. For these reasons, data pre-processing in this study was very fundamental in the images processing. First all the images in this study were checked against all forms of defects such as striping. The Landsat ETM+ and TM satellite data were processed using ERDAS imagine 14.0 image processing software performing various radiometric and geometric corrections.

Line band correction was applied to landsat7 of 2008 to correct for scan line error. After all necessary processing for radiometric and geometric corrections in order to preserve the radiometry and spectral information in the imagery, all datasets were brought under the same coordinate system (UTM zone 32N of WGS 84) in a GIS environment. Image enhancement using the software tools was used to increase the pictorial view of the post-processed images for proper visualization and analysis. The enhancement of the images was later performed as to improve their visual qualities. The images were later displayed as false colour composites with the band combination.

2.3 Digital Image Processing

The band combination adopted on imageries in this study were be 7, 4, and 3 for Landsat7 ETM+ images of 2008 and bands 7,5 and 3 for LandSat 8 image of 2018 which are convenient for ecological land use/land cover studies. Band 3(0.63-0.69um), Band 4 (0.77 um-0.90um), Band 5 (0.85-0.88um) useful for vegetation and water studies and band 7 (2.11-2.29um) a short infrared that clearly distinguishes wet soil from dry soil and also differentiates the earth structure. The band combination was

explorer. The images in their raw forms were exported to ArcGIS version 10.6 and geo-referenced to Universal Traverse Mercator (UTM) for digital image processing and map analysis. Various data enhancement techniques were utilized for better geo-visualization and reduce the effects of image distortions and enhance structural interpretation. Maximum likelihood classification was them used for image analysis, the data sets involved in these studies are primarily LandSat7 ETM+ 2008 and LandSat 8 operational imager, 2018. After geo-referencing and checking for proper alignments, the maps were fully digitized for feature extractions. The ArcGIS 10.6 was a very effective analytical tool due to its data inter-operability nature and spatial modelling capabilities as well as three dimensional visualizations of Imageries.

2.1 Data Sources

For this study, there was the identification of variables needed to carry our ecological risk zones mapping such as deforestation as well as variables for socio-economic and environmental analysis. The data sources were from access to databases and abstract that are presently available in various archives within specific periods. The primary data such as Landsat7 ETM+imageries (30m resolution)for the specific periods, 2008 (band 7,4,3 combination) and Landsat8, 2018 (band7,5,3) good for vegetation studies covering Bayelsa state was obtained from United State Geological Survey (USGS) database Explorer (www.earthexplorer.usgs.gov. (Global Land Cover Facility) acquired under good atmospheric conditions. and utilized after necessary data processing using secondary data sources.

2.2 Data Pre-Processing and Image

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conventionally utilized to produce a false or composite colour of images. Maximum likelihood classifier (MLC) classifier of the supervised classification algorithm running in the ERDAS Imagine software was used to categorize image land over classes. Training sites were generated from the imageries by capturing similar spectral reflectance on the imageries based on the knowledge gained from ground-truthing. This was used to carry out supervised classification and was performed on the two images of separate years acquired for the studies. The accuracy assessment done in this

study was the comparing of the classification data that are assumed which enabled the determination of the accuracy of the classifications within permissible accuracies.

2.4 Change Detection Method

The change detection witnessed in in this study was done using ERDAS version 14 and was then exported to ArcGIS 10.6 for feature extraction. The change detection was done on the final land cover/land use maps of this study to measure how the attributes of a particular area have changed between epochs 2008 and 2018.

3.0 Results and Discussions

Figure 3.1: Land Cover Distribution of the Study Area (2008)

Figure 3.1 shows a classified image map of 2008 with false colour composite. Four image classes were identified such as: built-up areas, mangroves, vegetation and water bodies with

varying compositions. The image as displayed shows more of vegetative covering over other classes and it was an enabling deforestation study acquired imagery.

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Table 3.1: Land Cover Distribution of the Study Area 2008

Class Name	Area(km²)	Percentage
Waterbody	549.3	5.80
Mangrove	2591.2	27.40
Vegetation	5610.1	59.2
Built Up Area	723.1	7.60
Total	9473.6	100.00

The results as shown in table 3.1 the various land cover classes using Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) which are: built-up areas having, mangroves, vegetation and water

bodies. The areas covered as shown in the table has 549.3km² for water bodies. 2591.2km² for mangrove, 723.1km² for built-up areas and 5610.1km² for vegetation.

Figure 3.2: Land Cover Distribution of the Study Area (2018)

Figure 3.2 indicates a classified image map of 2018 with false colour composite. Four image classes were detected which includes: built-up areas, mangroves, vegetation and water bodies

with varying percentages. It shows more of vegetation which was a key analytical factor in deforestation analysis.

Table 3.2: Land Cover Distribution of the Study Area 2018

Class Name	Area(km²)	Percentage
Water body	565.4	5.97
Mangrove	2611.1	27.60

Vegetation	5414.0	57.13
Built Up Area	885.7	9.30
Total	9476.3	100.00

Table 3.2 is a distribution of the classified image land cover characteristic of the imagery in 2018 using Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) which are: built-up areas, mangroves,

vegetation and water bodies. The areas covered as shown in the table 3.2 has 565.4km² for water bodies, 2611.1km² for mangrove, 885.7km² for built-up areas and 5414.0km² for vegetation.

Table 3.3 Accuracy Assessment of 2008 landcover Classification

Accuracy Totals						Kappa (K)
Class	Reference Totals	Classified Totals	Number Correct	Producers Accuracy	Users Accuracy	Kappa
Built up area	111	111	108	97.29%	97.29%	0.9670
Vegetation	73	73	70	95.89%	95.89%	0.9466
Mangrove	42	42	39	92.85%	92.85%	0.9201
Water body	30	30	30	100.00%	100.00%	1
Totals	256	256	247			Overall K =
Overall Classification Accuracy = 96.48%						0.9584

The accuracy assessment of the 2008 acquires satellite imagery was a supervised classification with an error matrix to show the level of accuracy of the classified imagery. The Kappa

value of 0.9584 with a classification accuracy of 96.48% gave an acceptable value to work with the acquired image under favourable conditions.

Table 3.4: Accuracy Assessment of 2018 land cover classification

Accuracy Totals						Kappa (K)
Class	Reference Totals	Classified Totals	Number Correct	Producers Accuracy	Users Accuracy	Kappa
Built up area	111	111	106	95.49%	95.49%	0.9410
Vegetation	73	73	65	89.04%	89.04%	0.8900
Mangrove	42	42	41	97.61%	97.61%	0.9755
Water body	30	30	30	100.00%	100.00%	1
Totals	256	256	242			Overall K =
Overall Classification Accuracy = 94.53%						0.9516

The reflectance values with an assessment of the 2018 acquired satellite imagery was also of a supervised classification with an error matrix to show the level of accuracy of the classified

imagery. The Kappa value of 0.9516 with a classification accuracy of 94.53% gave an acceptable value to enhance discussions of results.

Table 3.5 Comparison of Land Changes between 2008 and 2018 to detect deforestation Eteli T.H (Ph.D.), Odubo E. (Ph.D.) and Amatari-Breford Sinclair Amatari (Ph.D.)

Class	Area in 2008(km ²)	Area in 2018(km ²)	Change in Area(km ²)	% Difference (Gain/loss) in land cover type
Water Body	549.3	565.4	16.1	2.93
Mangrove	2591.2	2611.1	19.9	0.77
Vegetation	5610.1	5414.0	-(196)	3.4
Built-up Area	723.1	885.7	162.6	22.49
Total	9473.6	9476.3	2.7	0.029

Table 3.5 shows an analytical change detection in land cover characteristics within the study area in 2008 and 2018 covering a period of ten (10) years in order to detect deforestation from the remotely sensed satellite imageries in line with the study aim. Changes in vegetative cover as well as built-up areas gave an insight on how deforestation has taken place within the study area. Vegetation as a land cover in 2008 was 5610.1km² which changes to 5441.0km² in 2018 showing a loss of 196km² of about 3.4% loss in vegetative cover signifying deforestation. This could be as a result of extensive wood felling, agricultural and industrial processing such as oil exploration within the study area that has brought about forest loss. Similarly built-up areas in 2018 were 723.1km² and changes to 885.7km² with an increase in 162.6km² in area. This signifies rapid development that has taken. The change detection of water bodies can also reveal intense dredging and heavy amount of rainfall due to forest loss. The change in built – up area can also be attributed to rapid urbanization. Another factor that has led to degradation of the forest in the study area can also be large amount of oil spills that eventually affects vegetation.

4.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

Urbanization driven by human pressure on the exploitation of natural resources as well

agricultural purpose have posed a serious problem of deforestation in most parts of the Niger Delta. The study has revealed that the over –dependence on the use of wood for domestic, commercial, agricultural practices and industrial purposes has led to forest loss. Also, construction as well as oil and gas exploration within the study area have also contributed immensely towards the effects generated by deforestation which could also be attributed to exposure of top soil to heavy rainfall and precipitation hence the issues of soil erosion. Other effects could be habitat loss, coastal inundations as well as flooding. Change detection of land cover classes between 2008 and 2018 was able to give an insight on the rate of deforestation in the area. Built up areas increases while there was a vegetative loss in the image classification of the two epochs. The continuous use of geo-spatial techniques mostly the deployment of satellite imageries under good atmospheric conditions which could be analyzed in a GIS environment will assist a long way in effective environmental monitoring by policy makers as well as law enforcement agencies in the study area.

4.2 Recommendations

Following the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made in other to manage the said ecological risks in the study area.

1. There should be strengthened laws and enforcement in terms of policies and governance,
2. Public awareness on the effects of continuous deforestation,
3. There should be innovative and technological approaches to forests and natural resource

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- management,
4. There should be sustainable land use policy in the study area,
 5. There should be the continuous or periodic geospatial approach (further studies) for environmental monitoring.

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